

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING RESPONSIBLE ATTITUDE TO TRAFFIC RULES IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract.

This in the article school education in the system of young people road _ movement safety culture by increasing to go directly on the roads they are with depends unhappy of events reduction , this about the beginning class in students road movement to the rules responsible relationship formation methodology about word is conducted

Key words.

road movement safety , behavior rules , parallel education , logic thinking

INTRODUCTION

Har one state his own development young generation nature with tie by developing goes _ In this school education to himself special the ground task past , young people creative thinking the owner being growth , modern knowledge to take over service does _ We are young people all from the sciences initial concepts education in their homes acquisitions for in our country school of education free of charge done increase processes the law within strengthen we put Today to schools to our children education to give in the process all sciences row road movement safety rules according to in fellow students skills forming let's go it is necessary In ¹⁷⁰the students different sciences to know has been need like road movement rules and safety culture on the surface knowledge by increasing let's go his own to the field circle affairs in development positive the result gives _ Because each one grow up coming boys and girls diary of marriage indispensable to the moment turning around gone on the roads safety behavior to the rules action to do , way movement skills and habits by increasing to go it is necessary To the students road movement safety about knowledge giving as for them this occupied knowledge lifetime during , har always conscious social activity take on the way need will be

MAIN PART

¹⁷⁰ <https://roadsafetyweek.org/schools-colleges/2-uncategorised/69-road-safety-lesson-plans>

In society road _ movement safety including providing _ education in their homes each one education of the recipient personal safety care issue yet conscious and necessary natural social need as citizens by complete realize immature process is considered School in students conscious social responsibility of formation necessary from the conditions one this road movement safety culture moral behavior standards parallel education with _ School students for this norm and behavior the rules formation of the school main of duties one has been safety culture educate is the basis ¹⁷¹. This of the task separately complexity that is , the roads with depends of issues the solution external and internal obstacles overcame transition , child makes sense thinking to do to strengthen , to reality relatively school of teachers their will _ to the goal directed activities safety with is to bind . Only that's it way school of the student behavior road movement safety to culture will be directed and society for safety environment to the body brings _ In schools road _ movement the rules to the students constant respectively explaining on the go specialists process not only typical , perhaps extreme situations also information about giving to go , their philosophical mind get rich to go it is ¹⁷²necessary

Road movement security is _ children and young people attraction to do for great topic being especially " Road movement safety " week this done increase for great it's time ! If we from time right if we use it , students most of the time road movement safety according to reading and from training they enjoy and a lot concept and the rules because they learn this they are understand will receive and always need to be is an issue . Children and of young people road movement safety about concepts and relationships to form help give to them in his youth and when they are old security provide for the most good important is a possibility . Today's to the day come traffic accidents _ whole the world across of young people the most big is a killer ¹⁷³.

Road movement piles to teach in schools students of teaching one part to be need _ If so otherwise , road movement rules about messages another sciences according to in classes , meetings , lunch in training or if available if so , in general " civility " or " spirituality " lessons new topic before explaining transition need _

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We are below from 2 to 18 years old was different young groups what to teach according to some guidelines and lessons and training for some ideas , including

¹⁷¹ <http://kutubkhonachi.uz/documents/kitob/yo-l-harakati->

¹⁷² Uzbekistan _ Republic of Constitution . -Tashkent : Uzbekistan , 2018. Page 16.

¹⁷³ Hasan John Abdulmajid . Road movement jurisprudence _ - Tashkent : NIHOL-NASHR, 2021. Page 112 .

math , science, drama and English language such as sciences to teach addition possible was some thoughts we bring Today's in the day national or local authority from the joints defined representatives road movement safety to teach according to help and instructions school and Kindergarten to the students giving is coming and students between road movement safety how to teach need to show can _ Currently in our country road movement safety in charge persons by road movement safety according to study manuals and recommendations work developed and wide is being used ¹⁷⁴.

Road movement the rules from teaching before we students age and to the worldview attention our focus need _

2-5 years old students to teach

5-7 years old students to teach

7-11 years old students to teach

11-14 years old students to teach

14-18 years old students to teach

Road movement safety from teaching before , any a child in a traffic accident subject to was injured _ or serious to a traffic accident witness that it was checked without and their from needs come came out without approach need _ They are and their parents _ _ with " Auto on the subject of "catastrophes " . open discussion lesson training take to go need _ Road movement safety week organize reach or in it participation reach for you school or in your college others , in particular , the leader or directors council road movement safety to teach and promote to do from the start before his importance your persuasion need to be can _ Others to convince help giving one how many main thoughts :

- Child's on the roads each one death or serious injury family , wide public and of the child before school education institution , school or college for fatal being their _ each one prevention get can _ None a child is on the way own his life not to lose or terrible to injuries subject to not to be need _

- Road movement of safety evil not only of children injury or to die risk means maybe _ most of the time their health and impact on well - being does _ Many countries children between obesity (especially rich _ family in representatives) more and more is increasing , indeed they are regularly respectively walking and on a bicycle walking probability less than that while inactivity , obesity and social to development effect does _ Of this main reasons one

¹⁷⁴ <http://kutubkhonachi.uz>

the city and his around streets Dangerous if so , parents most of the time to their children walking or on a bicycle to walk permission to give they don't want

- Teachers to the students life save staying messages to teach and local in the area parents and drivers such as road movement safety more wider promote to do through the children protection to do and fatal events prevention in getting important role to play can _

- Schools and colleges local roads safer to do , especially children and to families safe on foot walking and on a bicycle walking enable creator pedestrians ways to build just like that is enough

- Road movement safety only small age children for not _ Children How big if so , to independence from achieving then , they with depends events more happen will be Many countries young drivers with participation car accidents big problem on the roads death of those who big part school students organize does , therefore vehicles for _ driving or passenger to be and different danger - from dangers alert to be and awareness teens too much for important _

CONCLUSION

Summary by doing so to speak , today in the day to young people road movement safety culture to teach about each one of the student alertness increase , spiritual in the world modern roads with depends concepts expand big important has _ This is us in progress to our youth necessary concepts before school education , school and higher education in joints continuously respectively by teaching we go , on the roads movement to the rules compliance to do community based on control by doing let's go need _ In schools each one of the student road movement safety culture upgrade important process is , har one of the citizen responsibility Demand reached remains .

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